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A general conceptual framework for multi-dimensional spatio-temporal data sets

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ABSTRACT

In the era of ubiquitous data collection and generation, demands are high to make these data accessible as widely as possible, with as little effort and as much power and flexibility as ever possible. On Earth data, this holds in particular for pixel data and point clouds, some of the main “Big Data” today. Coverages represent a unifying concept for space/time-varying data, especially for spatio-temporal gridded data, nowadays often called “datacubes”.

Coverage standards exist, however, their fundamentals appear in places technically outdated, imprecise, and not suitable for the full spectrum of data. Due to this lack there is a danger of missing interoperability goals and impeding future-directed “Big Earth Data” services.

We introduce the conceptual coverage model of the forthcoming ISO 19123-1 standard. It is generic, supporting all spatio-temporal dimensions in a unified manner, and is compatible with the existing coverage implementation standards of OGC and ISO. We demonstrate feasibility through concrete service examples.

1. Introduction

We are living in an era where it is as easy and inexpensive as never before to collect data about our physical environment at a large scale – both over large regions and over time. The same holds for artificially generated data such as climate simulation output. Storage and processing capabilities (The Big Data Volume and Velocity) today are less of a problem than Variety and Veracity, to continue using the V-terms. Gaining insight from data requires intensive work on finding, collecting, homogenizing, and combining them. Activities aiming to move “from files to pixels” and towards “analysis-ready data” (Wulder et al, 2016) herald the need for having data readily available for analysis and gaining insights, without spending the major part of the effort on data preparation.

High level general concepts help and give guidance for such data preparation, and based on them effective, scalable interfaces and complete services can be built. Standards can help to give guidance to implementers, but also foster interoperability of tools once widely adopted.

Mathematically, the realm of spatio-temporally extended phenomena can be captured by tensor fields; the corresponding concept in IT world establishing a data and (subsequently) service model is given by *coverages*. Coverages are multi-dimensional by nature – such as 1-D sensor timeseries, 2-D x/y images, 3-D x/y/t image timeseries and x/

y/z subsurface information, and 4-D x/y/z/t atmospheric and oceanographic information. The dimension axes spanning the coverage’s extent can be of spatial, temporal, or “abstract” nature (where abstract is understood in the sense of being neither spatial nor temporal), or any combination of these. As such, a coverage forms a digital representation of some space/time varying phenomenon. For example, a satellite image timeseries has two spatial and one temporal axis whereas a geo-statistical datacube may have a temporal axis, spatial extents, as well as thematic axes such as gender and age categories, providing the count of the relevant subset of the population as the range value. So the spaces to be considered definitely reach beyond 4-D x/y/z/t.

Coverages essentially serve to describe spatially (and possibly temporally) extended phenomena. The difference to a vector representation is that in such a coverage observations vary with location (and time). For example, a highway represented by a polyline will have a name like “A27” along all its extent, invariably – just one property is associated with the entire object. In a coverage view of the same highway, conversely, its degree of surface humidity might be captured to serve, for example, networked cars underway. Obviously, humidity varies individually along the extent of the highway, and additionally changes over time. Conceptually this is continuous with an infinite amount of information, but as sensors can deliver only a finite number of values the humidity technically is available only for a finite number of

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positions along the highway. With the help of some method of interpolation, humidity can be obtained also for positions between those where values are available directly, creating an infinite, continuous approximation of reality from a finite data set – with all the well-known caveats.¹

This small scenario highlights that coverages regularly are substantially more complex and voluminous data structures than vector data. In common terminology, coverages typically constitute Big Data. Establishing a conceptual model for coverages is challenging for several reasons. First, the intrinsic complexity of this concept is contrasted with the need of a handy model that is easy to use also for non-experts. Further, each of the diverse application domains bring along their own requirements and conventions, which need to be matched by the generic underlying model – otherwise, cross-domain data communication remains theory. Multiple problems need to be addressed, including: how to achieve a unified handling of multi-dimensional coordinates with space, time, or other semantics, and the corresponding coordinate reference systems; how to integrate different description methods, such as raster points, point clouds, and geometric models; how to deal with all the discretization problems that occur in the context of raster data; the variety of encodings which diverge in particular on the metadata captured; and many more.

Over the last twenty years, driven by substantial progress made in science and technology, the coverage concept has evolved significantly. Today, it is widely accepted among standardization bodies such as ISO, OGC, and INSPIRE, which in turn was a trigger for tool implementers to adopt coverages – a who’s who of open-source and proprietary tools support the OGC Coverage Implementation Schema (CIS) and Web Coverage Service (WCS) standards suites. Dozens of Petabytes of Earth data are being served operationally, through standalone services as well as critical-mass data center federations.

However, to the best of our knowledge, today there is no implementation spanning the complete universe of coverage structures, and even less so supporting combining all different coverage types. Typically, coverage-oriented tools concentrate on raster data while point clouds and meshes are dealt with independently. Raster-oriented coverage implementations traditionally address 2-D horizontal data such as orthoimages, DEMs, and thematic raster maps. Basically, 3D + grid data have been present in weather forecast and climate modelling since the early days of supercomputers; however, these were accessible only by a few experts having logins on the storage servers and deep technical knowledge on the specialized formats used. With the advent of Array Databases showing the potential of multi-dimensional analysis, such “datacube services” are increasingly getting in focus.

Attempts towards a model for spatio-temporally extended phenomena have been undertaken before, as we will discuss in detail in Section 2. In particular, the ISO 19123 standard, written in about 2000 and adopted in 2004, defines coverages.

The coverage model of 19123, developed around 2000, deserves renovation and cleanup in several respects. While it has been seminal in guiding coverage standardization, it no longer represents the state of the art. Among the many shortcomings are: some items are not described optimally with sometimes naïve definitions, such as the term “raster” which is defined as a “usually rectangular pattern of parallel scanning lines forming or corresponding to the display on a cathode ray tube”; treatment of grids is impractical and missing important cases; treatment of multi-dimensionality is neither homogeneous nor sufficiently general; the top-level distinction into discrete and continuous coverages blurs the picture and is not to the point, making the standard well known as a hard read. Finally, recent practice to split into fundamentals and implementation specifications requires a disentangling of concepts which in

¹ “It is virtually impossible for a representation, based on a discretization, to agree perfectly with the real world, so the choice of a comparatively accurate discretization is clearly important.” (ISO, 2004b).

19123 provide a confusing mix of concepts and implementation details.

Goal of our work is not to propose an entirely new model, but to accomplish consolidation. The article builds on work done by the editor of the forthcoming abstract coverage model standard, ISO 19123-1 (ISO, 2020c), based on initial work presented to ISO with DIN SPEC 18114 (Baumann and Merticariu, 2018) which forms the basis for the forthcoming 19123-1 Coverage Fundamentals standard as a companion to the adopted 19123-2 Coverage Implementation Schema (ISO, 2019c). We base our coverage work on the concepts of 19123, but give more concise and correct definitions of the underlying concepts and altogether provide a framework which focuses on the concepts rather than realization and reorganizes presentation to ease overview and understanding. For the same reason, a semi-formal approach is adopted which ensures succinctness while remaining understandable to readers without a background in formal semantics specification (Bauer and Wössner, 1982) as done by us, e.g., in SQL/MDA (ISO, 2019d) and OGC WCPs (Baumann, 2010) (Baumann, 2021-01c). Note that we do not attempt at establishing an API for Web services, nor a query model as in databases. However, we attempt at preparing the scene by establishing an expressive, interoperable coverage data model which is sufficiently complete and tractable for such next steps.

As such, this contribution aims at allowing sharing and discussion of the forthcoming standard, but also at discussing background, theory, and design rationales which do not fit into a standards specification document.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows. In Section 2 we inspect the state of the art. The conceptual coverage model is presented in Section 3, followed by a classification of key coverage types in Section 4. An overview on the impact of the model is given in Section 5, and Section 6 concludes the plot.

2. State of the art

Substantial work has been devoted in the coverage field on both conceptual and implementation level, even though it often was not labelled as coverages. We inspect the state of the art in mathematics/physics, Computer Science, and standardization. As this contribution deals with the fundamentals we put the main emphasis on conceptual work, and less on implementation (which will be the subject of a forthcoming companion paper).

2.1. Mathematics and physics

We start with the common abstract notion of coverages as “digital representations of space/time varying phenomena” (OGC, 2021). Various methods are known for representing phenomena that vary across some given space,² including analytical geometry, boundary representations, and the whole field of discretized pixel and voxel modelling.

A very generic model of spatially extended phenomena is provided by *Function Representation* (F-Rep) (Pasko et al., 1995), implemented in Hyperfun (n.n., 2021-01a). F-Rep represents shapes in n -D space as single real-valued functions $f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$. By definition, points with a function result above zero are inside the object, a value equal to zero indicates the border, called *isosurface*; values below zero define the outside of the object. This model is capable of handling non-manifold models as well as a mix of lower-dimensional entities, such as surfaces, curves, and points, in a unified manner. Discrete fields, such as voxel objects, will appear as discretized functions which can be interpolated to obtain a continuous function. This concept is complemented by *R-functions* describing set-theoretic operations; R-functions form the basis of the Hyperfun programming language. Further, a generalization

² We will use “space” as a summary term for “space, time, and other types of dimensions” whenever unambiguous; see discussion later in this contribution.

to a *constructive hypervolume* has been proposed (Pasko et al., 1995) which allows for modelling n -D point sets with arbitrary attributes. As such, F-Rep is very close to coverages. It seems like a worthwhile endeavour to describe coverages in terms of F-Rep and study operations with the goal of formally deriving coverage services; this might even lead to new coverage service paradigms.

A very interesting formalization of fields is undertaken by Liang, Nittel, and Hahmann using second-order functionals (Liang et al., 2016). This approach has proven successful already earlier on a subtype of fields, discrete multi-dimensional arrays (Baumann, 1999). Obviously, such formalizations are particularly suitable for defining the semantics of declarative query languages on such structures (Baumann, 2010; ISO, 2019d). Likewise relevant work has been published by Galton (Galton, 2004) who establishes a unified theory along a very similar line, but considering both fields and discrete objects in space and time.

The general mathematical concept behind all of those is that of a *tensor field* (McConnell, 1957). In Linear Algebra, a tensor is known to be an n -dimensional array, in 1-D called a *vector* and in 2-D a *matrix*. In practice, vectors often are replaced by records to offer the convenience of named instead of numbered components.

The set of points making up a tensor field's space resembles a *manifold* (Rehmann, 2020; Munkres, 1991), meaning that around every point that n -dimensional space behaves like a multi-dimensional Euclidean space which, simply put, means: each point has neighbouring points as we know it from physical space. In a grid, for example, which spans such a space every point has exactly two neighbours "above" and "below" the point's position on that axis (Fig. 1). In practice, where we deal with finite grids, the boundary points where no neighbours exist outside the grid limits constitute an exception to this rule. Generalizations of such a space, such as general Riemann spaces (do Carmo, 1992), have been discussed, however for practical relevance we stick with Euclidean space.

Finally, points in n -D space may be aligned along some *grid* of points, which may be *regular* with constant distances among neighbours or *irregular*. This actually is the prevailing structure for imagery, climate model output, and many more as especially square grids are convenient

Fig. 1. Symbolized Euclidean neighbourhood in a (discrete) manifold.

to handle through arrays in programming (Knuth, 1968). The most well-known grids have a "quadrilateral" shape.³ Let us determine what other grid types are possible in n -D space. Skipping the trivial 1-D case we find that in 2-D space there exist exactly three regular edge-to-edge tilings based on triangles, squares, or hexagons, resp. (Grünbaum and Shephard, 1977) (Coxeter, 1989), see Fig. 2. In 3-D the only useful grid is given by the cuboid, and likewise in 4-D space we find only the hypercube, also called *tesseract*. Also for higher dimensions cuboid equivalents are the only grids possible.

The description of a field's mapping from points in space to their associated values can be done in many ways. If the space is continuous then even a limited region, as coverages normally are, can contain a transfinite number of points which is impossible to represent in (finite) computer memory. Therefore, other means have to be found. One approach is to (finite or transfinite) cluster sets of points into a finite number of regions, and store some finite description of each region as a representation of the field. Depending on the spatio-temporal dimensions under consideration these regions can be given as 1-D curves, 2-D surfaces, 3-D solids, or 4-D time-variant solids, for example (ISO, 2019b). Note that such objects may well be embedded in some higher-dimensional space, such as a 2-D terrain surface draped on an elevation model in 3-D space.

Another method for describing a transfinite, continuous field is to use a finite set of 0-D points together with an interpolation method for obtaining values for points in between the ones stored (Sheppard-Chisholm, 1911).

Grids also occur naturally, e.g., at microscopic level. In crystallography a regular, repeated lineup of molecules, atoms, or ions is modelled by the mathematical structure of a (geometric/group theory) lattice (Bravais, 1850). Such a lattice may be viewed as a regular tiling of some space. The periodicity of regular grids, which allows computing storage location of a cell through a linear addressing scheme, corresponds to the periodic arrangement of the same particle or some regular patterns from a small number of particle types, called *motif*, in an ideal crystal.

The crystallographic restriction theorem, as per Coxeter (Coxeter, 1989), has it that in any dimension there is only a finite number of distinct lattice patterns. Closest to regular grids, as discussed in our geo context, are Bravais lattices (Bravais, 1850) which are generated by translations (corresponding to "resolution" in geo grids) along each axis. In Euclidean 2-D space there exist 17 different types of periodic tilings, based on groups of isometries. However, under the restriction that all cells have the same shape there are only three regular tiling types: square, triangular, and hexagonal tessellations (Grünbaum and Shephard, 1977).

Hence, the abstractions known in crystallography can provide a useful tool to determine the set of possible (regular) grids in 2D and higher dimensions. Aside from that, it is not a current interest of research to unify geodesy and crystallography, so we do not follow this approach further, just note in passing that spatial grids are known in a variety of disciplines and treated there in a diversity of formalizations.

In Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and its applications, like climate/weather modelling and aerodynamics simulation, grids are common. Partial differential equations as per Navier (Navier, 1822) and Stokes (Stokes, 1851) can describe the behaviour of gases and liquids (subsumed under *fluids*), and so numerical solver codes are common in these disciplines (Harlow and Welch, 1965). In the Earth sciences we find many examples, such as weather forecast, air quality monitoring, wildfire simulation, ocean surface modelling, and several more.

Specifically in numerical weather prediction, grids are often used which do not align with the grids common in GISs. Differences include a

³ A fundamentally flawed term as quadrilateral – i.e., "with four corners" – is adequate only for the 2D regular case with identical spacing on both axes, and the imaginary connection lines are neither in a 90° angle nor necessarily straight.

Fig. 2. 2-D regular tilings (Tomruen, 2021).

rotated latitude-longitude grid as well as using an icosahedron (which is not in our above list of suitable grids) instead of rectangular grids for the horizontal coordinates (Reinert et al., 2021). Vertical coordinates may rely on proxies such as pressure coordinate systems, and additionally reduce resolution for higher altitudes, which all make the vertical axis irregular (Lynch, 2006). A further noteworthy technique is ensemble modelling where various simulations are run in parallel; among other techniques, older simulations are continued to deliver forecasts for further time in future while in parallel new runs are started based on the latest actual observations. This leads to a second time axis, named wallclock time, in addition to simulated time. A coverage, therefore, must be able to hold more than one time axis, differentiated appropriately such as through unique axis name aliases.

While the time axis is regular in weather forecast, experience shows it may be irregular with satellite imagery. Hence, a mix of regular and irregular axes is common in coverage universe, which will give rise to a specific grid modelling in Section 4.3.

Along a different line, Arakawa (Arakawa and Lamb, 1977) has studied grid types which we will come back to later when introducing “pixel in corner” and “pixel in area” concepts.

2.2. Computer representations

Analytical geometry describing “inside” and “outside” of areas in the sense that positions inside such a geometric object – which might be a line, surface, or solid – own the properties associated with the object whereas locations outside don’t.

The stated target of coverages is regular and irregular grids, point clouds, and meshes (Baumann). A variety of representation schemes for coverages/fields is in common use, depending on the nature of the data and the operations applied to them. We inspect them in order of their topological dimension, going from 0-D points up to 3-D solids. A classification from an atmospheric research viewpoint is presented by Balaji and Liang (Balaji and Liang, 2021–01; Balaji et al., 2005). They use “grid” as the overarching term and avoid “mesh” at all. Generally, their definition is not underpinned by mathematical treatment, but follows a more informal, intuitive approach.

General *point clouds* basically are sets of coordinate/value pairs. An example for a common transformation of point clouds is thinning, where too similar points get eliminated to condense the data set. Frequently, though, point clouds serve to extract higher-level information through surface reconstruction and object recognition (Berger et al., 2016), visualization (Levoy and Whitted, 1985), etc.

Points that sit on some kind of grid are referred to as *gridded* or *raster data*. As there is substantial confusion about the terms grids and meshes let us first define both. A grid in our context means: all points involved have pairwise distinct positions in n -D space/time. Further, a connectivity criterion requires that every point has exactly two direct neighbours per dimension, one with a lower and another one with a higher coordinate value. In a Cartesian grid, also referred to as *raster*, the minimum distance in a grid is 1. Only at the outer boundaries of a grid may the number of neighbours per axis may reduce from two to one. Due

to this regularity of grid data, storage and processing is substantially more efficient than with point clouds, which explains the success of imagery in all Earth sciences.

Some grid mappings come at the expense of discontinuities. For example, the mapping to a cuboid presented in Fig. 3 contains some cells, like the ones in the center of the image, which do not have diagonal neighbours in all directions. In practice, software iterating over such a structure will have to implement expensive case distinctions for the discontinuities, and neighbourhood operations like convolutions may not return the expected result, but generate artefacts. Hence, such models tend to be not widely adopted, an example being the Discrete Global Grid System (DGGS) specification (Purss, 2017) relying on space-filling curves on hexagonal primitives.⁴

Walking up the dimension of the objects collected in a coverage we find 1-D curves, 2-D surfaces, and 3-D solids. We collectively name these *meshes*. There is a natural hierarchy in their modelling: points delimit curves, curves enclose surfaces, and surfaces constitute the boundaries of solids. These have been studied extensively in Computer-Aided Design and related domains, but also in the GIS area (Goodchild et al.,

Fig. 3. Mapping of a sphere onto a cuboid with discontinuities (Balaji and Liang, 2021–01).

⁴ Specifically DDGS as adopted in OGC has additional disadvantages, such as requiring the user to know the storage structure, as opposed to the principle of data independence proven highly useful in data management in general.

2007).

In Computer-Aided Design (CAD), *Boundary Representations* (B-Rep) are standard, which describe solids through hierarchical graphs whose nodes represent vertices, edges, faces, and solids to delineate arbitrary bodies, typically with the help of line and surface approximations like NURBS. B-Rep has been studied extensively, see for example (Braid et al., 1980) (Mäntylä, 1984) (Baumann, 1988) (Mahdiraji, 2015).

Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) is a method of describing general 3D bodies through parametrized primitives – like sphere, box, cylinder, cone, and ring – together with set-like operations for building hierarchical combinations of such primitives, thereby allowing generation of more complex shapes (Foley, 1996) (Requicha and Voelcker, 1982). In the coverage model such objects might be represented through expressions in some suitable language, such as MathML.

Given this wide range of variations we tentatively do not fix a particular one, but rather define an abstract dependency on some geometric model, be it B-Rep, CSG, or something else. Due to the normative character, this reference needs to target a standard, in this case is ISO 19107 (ISO, 2019b). Further relevant standards in the geographic domain include ISO 19125–1 (common architecture) (ISO, 2004b) and 19,5–2 (SQL binding) (ISO, 2004c), together with the OGC counterpart (Herring, 2011). Spatial data types are also defined in ISO 13249-3 SQL/MM Spatial (ISO, 2016).

Generally speaking, in the coverage context, the main emphasis so far has been on gridded data, such as satellite imagery, atmospheric simulations, and geophysical voxel data. Mesh data types have not yet been addressed systematically from a coverage perspective, not to speak about issues of integrating them and converting between different representations – starting with regular versus irregular grids, up to grids versus meshes. Notably, all these issues have been addressed in science and technology indeed, see (Worboys, 1995) for just a few examples; it is an open research question to establish a common model suitable for standardization.

2.3. Standards

2.3.1. OGC and ISO

OGC Abstract Topic 6 is OGC's abstract specification of coverages, developed around the year 2000; subsequently, it has been adopted verbatim by ISO as 19123:2004 (ISO, 2004a). The specification introduces data types which first of all are differentiated into *discrete* and *continuous coverages*. Discrete coverages fall into the subcategories *discrete point coverage*; *discrete grid point coverage*; *discrete curve coverage*; *discrete surface coverage*; and *discrete solid coverage* where the coverage domain is described by points, curves, surfaces, or solids, resp. Continuous coverages fall into *Thiessen polygon coverage*; *hexagonal grid coverage*; *segmented curve coverage*; *TIN coverage*; and *continuous quadrilateral grid coverage*. This grouping is not entirely motivated – for example, there is no continuous solid coverage; the relation between discrete grid coverage and a continuous quadrilateral grid coverage is not explained; irregular grids seem missing. In general, the selection of grid types appears neither complete nor orthogonal. Interpolation is defined incoherently and only for 2-D. Several definitions are outdated at best, in places unnecessarily involved, and often inexact, as the following examples illustrate:

- “Raster = usually rectangular pattern of parallel scanning lines forming or corresponding to the display on a cathode ray tube” – Aside from the partial definition applicable only “usually” this relies on some particular (in our days completely obsolete) hardware and constrains raster data to 2-D. A more modern definition would simply base on Cartesian grids.
- “Grid = network composed of two or more sets of curves in which the members of each set intersect the members of the other sets in an algorithmic way” – This leaves open what exactly is to be understood

by a “network” and what the “algorithmic” way mentioned should look like. Finally, it excludes the 1-D case.

Another criticism of 19123 is that it places its grounds on implementation-oriented data structures rather than on high-level concepts. This reflects the then-modern approach of packing all aspects, from concepts to data storage, into one specification whereas the modern approach in standardization establishes pairs of synchronized companion standards addressing concepts and implementation, respectively.

Such issues have contributed to an often-heard impression that coverages are complicating facts and of less practical use. One effect was that interpretations emerged which claimed conformance with 19123 while not being mutually compatible and interoperable, which also did not send a message of suitability into the stakeholder communities. Hence, while seminal in guiding coverage standardization for 15 years ISO 19123 is not any longer representing the state of the art. However, the interoperability issue of the implementation standards was felt to be most pressing, and consequently these were addressed first, coming to the fundamentals only recently. As the big picture was clarified in the beginning of this renovation effort it is ensured that all specifications, including forthcoming 19123–1, remain in sync.

In OGC, the Web Coverage Service Standards Working Group (WCS, SWG), recently renamed to Coverages, SWG, is in charge of the coverage standards. After a lack of acceptance of the WCS 1. x versions (Peter Baumann) – mainly due to undue complexity – a complete restart was launched, starting from scratch and abandoning the entire existing coverage approach. A separation into explicit data and service models was agreed, to enable provision via services beyond WCS. Further, the coverage model was based on the then-recent GML 3.2.1 model (Portele, 2007) as an improved, corrected, but backwards compatible version of its coverage model, thereby harmonizing coverage and GML worlds; for example, the original distinction into rectified and referenceable grid coverages is kept. The outcome was GML 3.2.1 Application Schema – Coverages (GMLCOV) 1.0 (Baumann) and its service companion, WCS 2.0 (Baumann, 2021–01a) (more on this in Section 5). After some time, unfortunately it turned out that the GMLCOV title caused significant confusion because it suggested this was just a GML encoding, not a general implementation model, and so in 2015 OGC decided to rename GMLCOV 1.0 to Coverage Implementation Schema (CIS) 1.0. CIS offers several grid types (Grid Coverage, Rectified Grid Coverage, Referenceable Grid Coverage), point clouds (Multi Point Coverage), and meshes (Multi Curve Coverage, Multi Surface Coverage, Multi Solid Coverage). The often unnecessarily complicated grid types have been augmented with CIS 1.1 General Grid Coverage (and WCS 2.1 (Baumann, 2021–01b) as companion) which can also handle coverage situations not previously addressed. At the same time, CIS 1.1 dropped some ballast inherited from GML. Finally, encodings for JSON and RDF were added. Altogether, CIS and WCS in combination ensure interoperability down to the level of single pixels through concise definitions accompanied by automated conformance tests.

Note that the relevant standards, both in ISO and OGC, are not always disjoint in all aspects. For example, an alternative (and different) realization of ISO 19123 data type *MultiPointCoverage* is given by the ISO 19107 data type *PointCloud* (ISO, 2019b).

2.3.2. INSPIRE

INSPIRE is the legal framework for a homogenized European Spatial Data Infrastructure. In its three Annexes it defines 34 spatial data “themes” and service requirements for practically all relevant geo data offered by agencies. These requirements have been further broken down to conceptual data models and concrete service specification guidelines. In 11 of these “themes” coverages play a key role (Fig. 4).

Several issues have been spotted in the INSPIRE coverage definition since its publication (Baumann and Escriu, 2019). However, a de-facto re-harmonization has happened through INSPIRE's use of OGC WCS,

Fig. 4. INSPIRE themes utilizing coverages (Baumann and Escriu, 2019).

normatively referencing OGC CIS and not the INSPIRE coverage model.

2.3.3. W3C QB4ST

The World-Wide Web Consortium (W3C) Spatial Data on the Web group, in collaboration with some OGC members, has established its own definition of a geo datacube, QB4ST (W3C). This approach is independent from and incompatible with OGC/ISO datacubes which uniformly are modelled through grid coverages. Main emphasis is on a list of metadata considered of particular importance, less so the data (i. e., direct positions and their associated values) themselves.

QB4ST expresses n -D datacubes in terms of RDF triples through a concrete RDF Data Cube ontology. The semantics of spatial axis coordinate values is given by CRSs as in coverages, the exact handling of time coordinates is not further detailed. Grids are constrained to be regular only. According to the specification document (W3C) QB4ST has draft status and should not be considered endorsed by the W3C membership at large. Several concepts are marked as “This is defined here pending availability of a canonical definition of spatial concepts - at which point an equivalence will be declared”. As furthermore no complete example is provided the potential merits of this model are not easy to assess.

3. A unified abstract coverage model

3.1. Anatomy of coverages

The term *coverage*, in line with the definitions of OGC Abstract Topic 6 (OGC, 2006) and ISO 19123 (ISO, 2004a), refers to a data representation that assigns values to positions in some multi-dimensional space. As such, a coverage can be viewed conceptually as a mathematical function which, for every value of its domain set, provides a particular value taken from its defined range set. As such, a coverage C is given by a function

$$C: D \rightarrow (P(V) \setminus \emptyset)$$

Where the *domain set* D of C is a non-empty set of *direct positions* (short for “directly stored values for a particular position”, as opposed to interpolation-derived) in some space and V is a non-empty set of values, called the *range set*, from which the function range values are taken. $P(V)$ denotes the power set of V . Each direct position always has at least one value assigned. More than one value might correspond to one and the same direct position as several observation results in a coverage overlap or even share the identical position. For example, in a point cloud two points may share the same positions. In a grid, on the other hand, by definition a grid cell contains exactly one value (which in practice may

be null).

The UML diagram of Fig. 5 sketches – on a high-abstract level – a coverage data structure that can represent domain and range set, plus further information discussed below.

In case of a finite domain set D the coverage can alternatively be written in pair-set notation:

$$C = \{ (p_1, v_1), \dots, (p_n, v_n) \} \text{ for } n = |D|, p_n \in D, v_n \in V$$

This notation of the coverage function often prompts an interpretation of coverages as just being sets of objects, in standardization typically referred to as *features*. While this view is not wrong (and coverages do not make a statement about any potential independent existence) it can be misleading: First, the coverage knows no other identification mechanism than the direct position. Second, despite the set notation we need to bear in mind that this set adheres to some specific rules; it cannot be concluded that naïve set operations will always work on coverages, and actually they often do not – a simple example is the union of two grids, which requires application of a transitive hull to the union set to again end up with a valid grid.

For our discussion we rely on the domain/range notation of a coverage while keeping in mind that further, equivalent descriptions exist. This situation is shown in the UML diagram of Fig. 5, which is extended with a range type description discussed later. Additionally, an optional metadata container is added which allows augmenting the coverage data with any kind of metadata; the coverage will not “understand” these data structures but transport them duly, thereby keeping connection between data and metadata. In practice, this often will be simply a reference into some catalog.

While mathematically this is perfectly equivalent to our function-based definition, it is our experience that using this definition can lead to considerable confusion among practitioners, as too often it is forgotten that such sets come with additional rules for the various subtypes which critically shape behaviour – simply put: a coverage is not just a set. For example, geometric features like curves, surfaces, and solids are assumed to have an interchangeable grid coverage representation consisting of a raster image. Obviously the mapping between raster and geometry is far from unambiguous, and in particular during rendering of a geometric shape into a grid, a substantial loss of accuracy and information content happens.

For these reasons we prefer the functional view as it allows conveniently expressing important coverage properties. That said, we will come back to this in Section 5 when discussing representation alternatives in computer storage. Further, a collection of concrete coverages encoded in XML, JSON, and RDF are available with OGC (OGC,

Fig. 5. Schematic structure of a coverage in the OGC/ISO coverage standards, simplified from (Baumann, 2012).

2021-01a).

In the remainder of this section we first abstractly define coverages through a probing function and then model each of the coverage constituents in turn.

3.2. Probing coverages

We make use of a *probing function* for defining the data. With the help of such a function, which delivers the coverage’s value for each of its direct positions, we can systematically observe the behaviour of an object – a principle dating back to the theory of algebraic specification of Abstract Data Types (ADTs) (Bauer and Wössner, 1982), where the objects under discussion remain opaque, defined only through their externally observable behaviour.

In case of coverages conceived as functions, associating values with coordinates, the appropriate probing function for extracting information about the data structure will retrieve the value associated with a particular point. Consider a coverage C with domain D and range set V . For every direct position within D , expressed in the coverage’s native CRS, the function *evaluate* () returns the set of values associated with this position:

$$evaluate_C: D \rightarrow V, evaluate_C(p) = \{ v \mid (p, v) \in C \}$$

Note that this probing function only serves for definition purposes, it is not required to be implemented. In practice, higher level retrieval functionality is desirable, such as bounding box subsetting in the OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS) Core (Baumann, 2021-01a).

3.3. Coverage domain

3.3.1. Definition

The coverage’s domain set describes for which positions in the coverage’s multi-dimensional space values are available; these are the “directly” stored positions, therefore they are called “direct positions”; further values may be generated via interpolation. The coverage domain describes some n -dimensional space, for some $n \geq 1$; for closure reasons we could consider single, position-less scalars as 0-D coverages, but this is not relevant for the purpose of this paper.

The multi-dimensional space the coverage provides data for is defined through the domain’s Coordinate Reference System (CRS). Every coverage is described by exactly one such CRS – its *native CRS* – which defines the domain space through a sequence of axes. Sometimes predefined CRSs contain everything needed (such as EPSG 4979 which contains two horizontal axes and one vertical axis), but if such a predefined CRS is not readily available then it can also be built on the fly through a compound CRS where axes as well as potential “sub-CRSs” are lined up in proper sequence (such as a composition of said EPSG 4979 with a time axis to describe a 4D space/time CRS). In OGC, CRSs (like other entities) are defined through URLs; an example for a compound CRS is the following:

[http://www.opengis.net/def/crs-compound ?
1 = http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326
& 2 = http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/0/AnsiDate](http://www.opengis.net/def/crs-compound?1=http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326&2=http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/0/AnsiDate)

Discussion is underway in OGC to allow simplified representations, such as the alias below as an equivalent to the URL-based identifier:

EPSG:4326 + OGC:DateTime

The EPSG catalog (OGP, 2021) contains several thousand (mostly horizontal) CRSs. Further CRSs and axes are under consideration by OGC, such as pressure altitudes, various calendars, and more. Planetary bodies have shown to be amenable to coverage standards as well (Oosthoek et al., 2014; Rossi and Hare, 2016), and there are about 2500 celestial CRSs maintained by the International Astronomical Union (IAU) currently. As per ISO 19111 (ISO, 2019a), OGC additionally foresees for a modular composition of CRSs from single axes and other CRSs (Misev et al., 2012).

The CRS defines the theoretically available space for direct positions, in practice bounded by minimum and maximum coordinates for each axis, together forming the coverage’s minimal bounding box. Note that if not stored explicitly it may be computationally expensive to determine the bounds from the domain set, as we will see later when inspecting various coverage types.

In a service which potentially offers a large number of coverages – such as Mundi datacubes with more than 2500 objects (n.n.b) – it is helpful if the coverage gives a hint about its location in a common, rather than its native CRS. To this end, in addition to its concise domain set, a coverage carries a so-called envelope which gives the approximate location and shape of the coverage through a (not necessarily minimal) bounding box; for horizontal geo coordinates this is typically provided in WGS84. One possible reason for the envelope being larger than the domain set is that the envelope bounding box, which must completely contain the coverage domain, usually is rotated and distorted relative to the native CRS bounding box. This allows for an efficient rough search across large coverage sets, for example to determine overlap with a particular region.

3.3.2. Mathematical vs physical coordinates

The coverage concepts presented in this work are agnostic of the real-life semantics of its dimensions. Geographic data typically have a subset of the following axes: two horizontal axes, one height axis (expressing elevation or bathymetry), and time. Climate and weather modelling add another time axis for differentiating model run time from the time modelled (though these are tightly correlated). A height axis can be replaced by a proxy such as pressure altitude. In aeronautics, pressure altitudes measured in hekto-Pascal (hPa) are considered, but also more abstract proxies such as Flight Levels, expressed in 100 ft steps like “FL150” for 15,000 ft above some reference point (mean sea level under the ICAO standard conditions (ICAO, 1993)).

Non-spatio-temporal axes occur in practice as well. For example, bands in hyperspectral imagery make sense as a numbered sequence in cases where there are hundreds of bands, such as the Hyperion instrument on board of EO-1 with its 220 bands (Pearlman, 2001). Also in geostatistics non-spatio-temporal dimensions are frequent.

Note also that originally spatial dimensions might become non-spatial at some level of generalization. For example, cities in Europe

might originally be expressed through coordinates, but at some higher level get abstracted to be in Bavaria, in the Alps region, etc. which is at a symbolic level.

Generally speaking, “abstract” (in the sense of non-spatio-temporal) axes may occur as well, like in OLAP where, e.g., time/product/subsidiary axes are common. For high-performance optical sensors as used in remote sensing and astronomy, spectral frequency can define a coverage axis as well. Spatial, temporal, and abstract axes may be mixed freely in a coverage domain definition in applications such as in spatial OLAP. We are aiming at a level of abstraction which allows sufficient spatio-temporal semantics while not excluding abstract dimensions, and any mix of all of those.

3.3.3. Topological vs geometric dimension

We distinguish the topological dimension of a coverage from its geometric dimension. The topological dimension is given by the degrees of freedom the domain set offers; for example, the topological dimension of an orthoimage is 2, given by its “flat” grid underlying the domain set. The geometric dimension aims at the length of the coordinate vector required to describe the coverage coordinates. For a “flat” orthoimage this will be 2-D coordinates, so topological and geometric dimension coincide, but the coordinates could also be, e.g., 3-D with a vertical component; in this case, the geometric dimension of the coverage is 3, hence larger than its topological dimension. In general, the topological dimension d_t of a coverage is less or equal to its geometric dimension d_g : $d_t \leq d_g$.

3.4. Common point rule

Except in grids, it may happen that coverage cells coincide. Points in point clouds may incidentally share the same direct position, multi-curve and multi-surface coverages may contain points where several lines meet, and curves, surfaces, and solids in a coverage may intersect or even be identical.

Many applications, however, are not prepared for such a set-oriented treatment and can only deal with one value per position. For such cases the coverage may provide a preference rule, the so-called common point rule, to pick one value in case of co-location of direct positions and declare it as “the” coverage value of this direct position.

Generally, a common point rule cpt_C is a function pertaining to a coverage C and a particular direct position p within the domain D , and delivering a single value out of the options offered by the coverage at that position:

$$cpt_C: D \rightarrow V, \text{cpt}_C(p) \in \text{evaluate}_C(p)$$

The choice of the rule may be controlled through an extra parameter. For example, ISO 19123 provides a code list with common options as follows (adapted to match this article’s terminology):

- average – mean of the cell values,
- low – minimum of the cell values,
- high – maximum of the cell values.
- all – set of all of the cell values.
- start – start value of the second segment in a segmented curve coverage.
- end – end value of the first segment in a segmented curve coverage.

Beyond this 19123 definition, the following additional options have been proposed:

- oldest – value with the least future-directed time coordinate (only applicable to coverages with a temporal axis).
- newest – value with the most future-directed time coordinate (only applicable to coverages with a temporal axis).

This seems due to a misinterpretation of spatio-temporal coordinates – time is just another axis, and hence direct positions which differ in the time component actually are distinct and do not need any choice method. In OGC WCS (Baumann et al., 2018), for example, a timeseries extraction at one spatial point would naturally yield the sequence of points with their proper time coordinates associated, as a 1-D coverage – see Section 5.1 for an example. The intended effect, to pick a particular value along the time axis, is accomplished through subsetting (see WCS discussion in Section 5.2). Therefore, we disregard oldest and newest.

ISO 19123 extends the Common Point Rule to coverages which allow interpolation as follows: at positions in between direct positions the interpolation is performed first, and the Common Point Rule is applied on the resulting values.

We have some general reservations over this Common Point Rule. First and foremost, making a choice out of existing values appears forceful and effectively hides some values in the coverage from the user. Further, the options provided seem arbitrary and lack a common concept – one option returns a set of values, all others return single elements, without motivation. Also, start and end address only multi-curve coverages, as one very specific category, while other relevant cases, such as surfaces and solids, remain unaddressed. Also average, low, and high might be augmented with, say, median as further option, so this is by far not closed and final. In passing we note that we are not aware of any implementation supporting this functionality.

For these reasons – and despite being aware that the forthcoming 19123–1 will keep it – we abandon the concept of a common point rule altogether, and define the coverage evaluation function to always return a set of values. In case this is undesirable (such as with grids where the grid points are expected to have a non-zero pairwise distance) we express this through explicit constraints. Algorithmic aspects, such as in overlay operations which require a choice to hide values of “lower” layers in presence of non-null values in “higher” layers of a map stack, get adequately addressed in the corresponding service operation definition.

3.5. Coverage range and coverage range type

Mathematically, the range set equals its type, so V says it all. In practice, however, this is insufficient. First, coverages must carry type information for proper decoding in an application – it might not be entirely clear what values like “FL050” or (1.0,-5.0) mean (is the latter an imaginary number? or wind components?); in Computer Science syntax, coverages require dynamic typing, and so the receiving tool must get this information which may or may not be deducible from the values themselves.

Second, applications require substantially more semantics than just the programming language’s data type. Among the essential information are units of measure (meters, degrees, etc.), null values (such as –9999 which is often used in bathymetry), accuracy, measurement methodology and more. An example for a high-level semantic description of the value set is given by the OGC Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) Common DataRecord (Robin, 2011), which supports the description of any data structure that sensors or data generators may deliver. The DataRecord structure is used in the implementable companion standard of 19123–1, Coverage Implementation Schema (Baumann et al., 2021b) (ISO, 2019c), thereby enabling seamlessly passing of sensor information captured upstream to downstream coverage services.

3.6. Interpolation

Interpolation is a method for constructing new range values for coordinates within the domain set of a coverage which are aligned with direct positions (the only positions for which the coverage explicitly provides values). This can be useful for estimating values where none are present. Notably, interpolation (as opposed to extrapolation) derives values for positions between direct positions.

For example, in an image timeseries having Latitude, Longitude, and time axes, several ways of interpolation may become relevant:

- Linear interpolation along Latitude and Longitude (“bilinear interpolation”), with temporal resolution unchanged (in plain words: all existing timeslices get extracted) meaning no interpolation occurs along time.
- Interpolate each pixel’s history (i.e., along time) using linear interpolation, without any spatial interpolation.
- Linear interpolation along Latitude, Longitude, and time simultaneously (“trilinear interpolation”).

In principle, any point in the transitive hull of the domain set is amenable to interpolation. We denote the transitive hull of some coverage C , which in general is a superset of $\text{domain}(C)$, as $D^+(C)$ and define function $\text{interpolate}()$ as an extension to $\text{evaluate}()$, where $\text{interpolate}_C(p) = \text{evaluate}_C(p)$ for all $p \in \text{domain}(C)$:

$\text{interpolate}: C, D \rightarrow V$ with $D = D^+(C)$, $V = \text{range}(C)$

Many interpolation methods are in use, the most prominent being nearest-neighbour and polynomial (such as linear, quadratic, and cubic); less used methods include barycentric (on TINs) and lost area (for Thiessen polygons and hexagonal grids).⁵

As the interpolation function is based on the coverage domain and range type, these may impose natural restrictions on the type of interpolation applied. First, we inspect the domain set impact. Note that the domain set type (as an analogy to range type) is given by the CRS, more specifically: the axis definitions.⁶

- Index grid coordinates, representing integer numbers, do not allow expressing any in between value as it would not be an integer anymore; therefore, interpolation is not possible simply due to the lack of points that are not direct positions.
- Physical coordinates like Latitude, Longitude, height, and time are expressed through real numbers and, consequently, allow expressing values between direct positions.

Interpolation methods may go over a single axis or over several axes in combination. In an x/y/t image timeseries datacube one might want to apply bilinear interpolation along Lat/long and, independently, perform nearest-neighbour interpolation along time.

Next, let us see examples of how the range type choice can affect interpolation:

- Polynomial interpolation on a real-valued range type (such as radiometric intensities) would deliver as interpolation result some value “between” the contributing direct positions delivering more or less “smooth” transitions.
- A categorical range type, such as land use, does not allow arbitrary values as interpolation results, thereby restricting the choice of interpolation methods – e.g., polynomial interpolation is not applicable whereas nearest-neighbour is.

Bottom line, while the choice of applicable interpolation methods is to some extent determined by the domain and range data type, there is still a degree of choice. Therefore, we associate with a coverage a (possibly empty) set of applicable interpolation methods. Any tool processing a coverage should only apply those methods listed to not

⁵ The firm grounding of ISO 19123 in 2-D remote sensing shines through by mentioning bi-linear, bi-quadratic, and bi-cubic methods, rather than their general n-D counterparts.

⁶ Although today’s available CRS definitions do not convey this information explicitly – neither human nor machine readable the fact is recorded that, e.g., Latitude and Longitude are represented by real values.

violate the coverage semantics. Conceptually, a coverage with several interpolation methods (which all will yield different interpolation results) defines a family of coverages where, all members contain the same values at the direct positions themselves, but will convey potentially different values for the interpolated non-direct positions.

On a side note, one might also consider interpolation between components of the range values, such as in a combined handling of red, green, and blue channels together. However, we feel that this is entering into the field of general analytics and do not include such methods specifically under interpolation.

3.7. Discrete and continuous coverages

Based on the previous elaboration we now can define discrete and continuous coverages. An axis is called discrete if every possible interval with finite bounds describes a finite set of values, otherwise such an axis is called continuous. A coverage is called discrete if its axis list contains only discrete axes. A coverage is called continuous if its axis list contains at least one continuous axis. The new ISO 19123-1 lists a series of examples for illustration (ISO, 2020c):

- A map of postal code zones is a coverage which is discrete in its range. The postal code zones cover an entire country and at every location in the country one can evaluate the coverage function and get a value that represents the postal code for that location. Within a postal code zone the value is constant. One cannot interpolate such a discrete coverage.
- A coverage that maps a set of polygons to the soil type found within each polygon is a coverage which is discrete in its range.
- A point set representing a set of measurements that are only valid at the position of each point, and which cannot be interpolated, is a discrete coverage (discrete in domain).
- An image, sampled by a sensor, may be represented as a grid coverage consisting of a set of pixels corresponding to grid cells in the domain of the coverage. A value is associated with each grid cell. However, since the coverage is continuous an interpolation function – such as linear, quadratic, or cubic – may be applied so that a continuously variable value may be determined at any location within the domain extent of the image.
- In a coverage that maps direct positions in San Diego County to their temperature at noon on a specific day, both domain and range may take an infinite number of different values. This continuous coverage would be associated with a discrete coverage that holds the temperature values observed at a set of weather stations (discrete in domain), whereby the measured values correspond to a point set coverage. This point set coverage is discrete because each point can only have one value. The associated continuous coverage uses the point values as driving values for the coverage function and allows interpolation between the points.
- A set of bathymetric soundings is a discrete point set coverage with a single measured water depth value at each point location (discrete in domain). An associated continuous coverage allows one to interpolate between the measured depth soundings to determine the bottom surface of a body of water.
- Evaluation of a triangulated irregular network involves interpolation of values within a triangle composed of three neighbouring point value pairs.

Hence, the distinction between discrete and continuous is not a primary, first-class criterion, but a consequence of particular coverage properties. Historically, in ISO 19123 this has been the first-level differentiation of coverages, a well-known reason for sustained confusion.

3.8. Metadata

In practice, more data is necessary for providing relevant context –

think of the satellite instrument pixels are coming from, spectral characteristics of the sensor, processing steps applied, etc. In common terminology, further metadata need to be associated with a coverage. Given the foundational nature of coverage data, such metadata have to satisfy a wide range of domains. Unfortunately, despite standards like ISO 19115 (ISO, 2020a), and INSPIRE metadata (INSPIRE) there is not a generic concise, agreed definition of what this metadata should comprise; even worse, even within focused domains frequently there is no accepted consensus.

Confusion about metadata is as old as the term itself, yielding sentences like “your metadata are my data”. We have encountered the same in discussions about coverages; for example, sometimes the domain set is considered metadata, sometimes data (as it is part of the coverage concept). In reality, we observe several distinct levels of metadata (Fig. 6) pertaining to coverages. At the lowest level, the range set sits as “the data” of concern. These are described by the second level that we call technical metadata in the sense that they are indispensable for accessing the range set values. Among these are, for example, the underlying domain definition with its CRS and the range data type. One level above, geo descriptors add location and temporal information to the coverage’s range values. Here we find geographic and temporal coordinates, CRSs, and units of measure of the range values. These levels together constitute the coverage concept. On top of that, applications may add any type of further metadata, such as provenance information.

Therefore, as a way forward, in the concrete Coverage Implementation Schema (Baumann et al., 2021b) we have foreseen a slot for metadata in general, with an undefined structure to allow any type of data to be stored there – from simple references to a corresponding catalog record up to elaborate records describing the contributing footprint for each patch inside the coverage. The coverage will not know about the semantics of these metadata, but it will duly carry them along, thereby at least maintaining connection between data and metadata.

3.9. Internal structuring of coverages

The abstract concept of a function mapping direct positions to values can be modelled through various different data structures. While this may rightfully be considered an implementation detail and, hence, out of scope on the level of abstraction of this paper and ISO 19123-1 we still provide it as a guidance for possible concretizations, and as a bridge to the concretization of ISO 19123-2 and OGC CIS where several alternatives are broken down to concrete encodings in XML, JSON, and RDF. The UML diagram in Fig. 7 summarizes them.

One method of storing the domain/range function mapping is through a set of coordinate/value pairs. This approach is particularly convenient for timeseries streaming.

A complementary approach makes use of two collections, one for the direct positions of the domain set and the other for the corresponding range values. Both can be correlated unambiguously via their position in the collection. This scheme is attractive because there are very efficient methods for representing the domain set, particularly in case of regular

grids; the values in this case form a multi-dimensional array, where value positions can be computed for retrieval. In combination with range set compression, this leads to very storage-efficient encodings.

The two modes of organization described above represent extremes of a wide space of possible schemes: while coordinate/value pairs have the finest granularity (single positions) and, consequently, the largest number of items, the domain/range representation consists of one single “monolithic” item. In between is the universe of tilings, i.e., partitioning following some (regular or irregular) pattern. Specifically for very large gridded data sets tiling is highly advantageous, be it for efficient retrieval in datacube engines (Baumann et al., 2010), or for efficient extraction from large files in formats like TIFF (n.n., 2021-01b) and NetCDF (n.n., 2021-0a), where it is often referred to as chunking. Often such tilings are simple with regular tile sizes and shapes, but they can be irregular as well, such as for adjusting to particular access patterns. A comprehensive study of tiling patterns has been accomplished by Furtado (Furtado and Baumann, 1999). OGC/ISO CIS version 1.1 supports arbitrary tiling, and even organization into sub-coverages under certain homogeneity conditions (Baumann et al., 2021b).

A completely different approach is possible if the coverage function can be described analytically. In this case, the range set does not have to be materialized; instead, a definition of a generating function is stored in some suitable format like MathML. While there is little practical relevance for grid coverages and point clouds it is a widely used method in 3D CSG modelling in CAD/CAM.

4. Coverage typology by dimension

4.1. Overview

In this section, we establish classes of coverages aligned with the relevant application areas of coverages. These types in a nutshell are grids, point clouds, and general meshes. Instead of using this directly, we employ a more structurally justified classification based on the topological dimension of the elements describing the direct positions within a coverage, starting from ordered and non-ordered 0-D points (with gridded data being a special case) and moving up to higher dimensions (Fig. 8). We stop at full 3D x/y/z space acknowledging that higher dimensions are possible – however, to the best of our knowledge there are no practically relevant applications. That said, the hierarchy and data structures can be extended at any time without affecting the lower-dimensional levels. For example, the spatial dimensions and their characteristic behaviour in the coverage types may well be augmented with temporal and other axes, such as to model time-varying solids.

In the following subsections coverage types are introduced sorted along their topological dimension.

4.2. Multi-point coverages

A point cloud or multi-point coverage is a coverage whose domain set consists of a set of points; in other words: direct positions are unconnected points in the domain set given by their (point) coordinates. The evaluation function, consequently, specializes as follows for some coverage C and position p :

$$\text{evaluate}_C(p) = \{ v \mid \exists \text{ point } x \in \text{domain}(C): x = p, v \in C(x) \}$$

4.3. Grid coverages

4.3.1. Anatomy of grids

By far the most important application of coverages today is given by raster data, i.e., data sitting on some grid, long known as raster images and, more recently, as (Earth) datacubes (Baumann et al., 2021a), which have first been introduced in (Baumann, 1992) (Baumann, 1994). In

Fig. 6. Levels of metadata in coverages.

Fig. 7. Coverage domain/range structuring as UML diagram (ISO, 2020c).

Fig. 8. Coverage classification as UML package schema, simplified from (ISO, 2020c).

standardization, these are all modelled through the family of grid coverages, a special case of a multi-point coverage, where all direct positions are constrained to sit on some grid in the coverage domain.

Formalization of regular and irregular grids is straightforward. We

call $A_C = (a_1, \dots, a_n)$ an axis sequence, remembering it is determined by the coverage's native CRS, just as is the dimension n of the coverage domain. Along each axis a_i we pick a non-empty subset of points G_{i_j} in practice, each such set will be finite with, $k_i > 0$ elements, so we can

write it as

$$G_i = \{ g_{i,1}, \dots, g_{i,k_i} \}$$

We now can define the grid coverage domain as a set of direct positions

$$G = G_1 \times \dots \times G_n = \{ (g_1, \dots, g_n) \mid g_i \in G_i \text{ for } 1 = i \leq n \}$$

Topologically, every inner point in a grid has exactly two neighbours along each axis, one with a lower coordinate value and another one with a higher coordinate value along this axis. Border cells have exactly one such neighbour cell each in direction of the grid's border, corner cells have exactly one neighbour in each direction. This neighbourhood relation can be considered indicative to distinguish grids from meshes, in particular in discussions where mathematical language is better avoided.

In comparison, the definition of a grid in 19123 was a “network composed of one or more sets of curves in which the members of each set intersect the members of the other sets”; obviously, this excludes the 1-D case, and further does not prohibit touching and crossing of the generating curves.

As a first classification such an n-dimensional grid is said to be regular if, for all pairwise neighbouring direct positions, the distance in each axis is constant; otherwise the grid is called irregular. This corresponds to the definition of Rectified Grid Coverage and Georeferenceable Grid Coverage, resp., in the ISO 19123 standard under revision; a more fine-grain distinction, adopted in 19123-1, we will be introduce below. In passing we note that the lower and upper bound along each domain axis defines the minimum bounding box as expressed in the coverage's native CRS. Often (Portele, 2007) (Baumann) the minimum and maximum values, respectively, are grouped into diagonal corner points for defining the grid extent.

By construction, direct positions in a grid are pairwise disjoint: for each direct position there is exactly one associated value in the range of the function. A direct consequence is that in a raster image every pixel can contain only one value – overlaps resulting in several pixel values for some given coordinate are not admissible. We argue that this is actually natural from the viewpoint of analysis-ready data – while overlaps, say, of satellite scenes is common during acquisition and processing, both human users and image processing tools get confused and have to pay extra attention to artefacts resulting from acquisition (such as overlapping tracks) which get cleared during generation of more analysis-ready products such as for datacubes. Raw satellite swath data can be modelled as individual (irregular) grid coverages as well, they just cannot be combined into one coverage due to their non-matching grids.

Fig. 9. Sample 2-D and 3-D grids: regular, irregular, warped nest (from top left to bottom left), combination of regular Lat/Long with irregular time (center), combination of warped Lat/Long nest with irregular time (right) (Baumann and Merticariu, 2018).

4.3.2. Axis-based grid specification

The classical subdivision into Rectified (i.e., regular) Grid Coverages and Referenceable (i.e., irregular) Grid Coverages is rather coarse and does not allow expressing relevant details such as all grid types shown in Fig. 9. For example, a case which we frequently meet in practice when building datacubes (n.na) is timeseries on orthoimagery. In this case, the horizontal part of the 3-D grid is regular whereas distribution along time typically is irregular (Fig. 9 center). In traditional nomenclature this would simply be a general referenceable grid, neglecting the regularity of the spatial axes – thus causing excessive storage and processing overhead in practice, as the more expensive general representations for irregular grids will be used by the system, rather than the efficient regular grid mechanics. In the classical Rectified Grid Coverage of the original 19123 standard, this cannot be represented as one axis is irregular; rather, this needs to be modelled as a 19123 Referenceable Grid Coverage, where all axes are considered irregular, leading to a massive storage and processing overhead for those axes which actually are regular and can be described by a simple resolution value.

Therefore, we propose to abandon the classification into several grid types and instead advocate a more fine-grain distinction which considers each axis individually for the direct position's regularity properties. This leads us to the following axis types (cf. Fig. 10):

- An Index Axis is a 1-D Cartesian axis: there is no geo-reference, admissible coordinates for direct positions are at discrete integer positions and unit-less (technically expressed by a unit of 1), and there is no datum mapping defined which could relate to some physical position. As a consequence of the discrete nature of the axis, no coverage interpolation is possible between adjacent coordinates.
- A Regular Axis has an equi-distant spacing like an Index Axis, but is continuous and not constrained to integer positions and distances. Such an axis can be georeferenced, i.e.: it can have a spatial or temporal semantics attached. Units of measure – typically degrees, meters, seconds, years, etc. – are defined with the axis CRS, which also should specify meaningful interpolation.

Due to the regularity, valid coordinate positions can be expressed as multiples of a given distance (the resolution) added to an initial offset (the lower bound coordinate).

- An Irregular Axis is continuous, possibly geo-referenced; the distances between neighbouring points are non-zero, but otherwise arbitrary.
- A Displacement Axis Nest (or Warped Nest) is a set of continuous, possibly georeferenced axes, forming a subset of the grid's axes. Relative to a regular grid, each direct position is shifted by some

Fig. 10. UML model of grid axis variants (Baumann and Mercicariu, 2018).

individual offset within the CRS space spanned by the axes participating.

In the extreme case, such a nest spans all axes of the grid, which resembles the Referenceable Grid of earlier standards.

- Algorithmic Axes are given by a set of discrete or continuous, possibly geo-referenced axes where the actual coordinates are not indicated, but have to be derived algorithmically from some otherwise abstract parameter set provided (hence, the alternative name transformation model). Nature, data type, and evaluation of such parameter types is tentatively left unspecified, but must be defined on an application specific basis.

Examples of such algorithmic axes include sensor models where, instead of the coordinate information, a set of sensor parameters (such as ground control parameters) is provided, which must be fed into the model for deriving the actual direct positions.

By combining all the above axis types freely, any type of grid can be modelled. We can substantiate this claim with the observation that not only are the common well-known cases represented, but the warped nest allows to effectively assign individual positions to each direct position in the grid as long as the basic grid definition is not violated (ordered positions, positive distance between grid “lines”). Still, the list of possible axis types is not comprehensive; some standards or applications may define their own specialized axis types.

Comparing this with the previous classification of grid coverages (Baumann), we can easily map them into this new schema:

- rectified grid coverages are those where the underlying grid consists of only regular axes;
- referenceable grid coverages are all those where the underlying grid consists of at least one irregular axis.

It is easy to see that the axis-based classification allows substantially more fine-grained differentiation in the universe of regular and irregular axes. Furthermore, several classes of coverages can be described now which were not supported by the earlier classification, namely: warped nests, algorithmic axes, and all combinations of the various axis types described.

4.3.3. Further grid types

In Section 2 we have discussed the grid types possible in Euclidean n-space and found that cuboid grids exist in any dimension while in 2-D triangular and hexagonal grids additionally exist, constrained by the fact that the axes for coordinate expression must be straight, uninterrupted lines in the tiling pattern in each dimension (which includes skewed, non-orthogonal axes since simple coordinate translations can be found). The hexagonal case at first glance seems to contradict this. However, with a trick this case can be mapped back to the square case, by considering as direct positions not the grid corners, but the hexagon centers (Fig. 11). This situation can be described through a rectified grid in which the two offset vectors are of equal length, but differ in direction by 60°. The length L of a side of the hexagon is $L = S \times \tan(30^\circ)$, where S is the length of the offset vector. In a computer the values of such a coverage range can therefore be stored as a multi-dimensional array, with an adjusted index addressing scheme. By way of background, the hexagons are the Thiessen polygons generated around the grid points.

Altogether, after this inspection we can confirm that square and – with less relevance – triangular and hexagonal grids are the only grid-generating patterns possible for coverages.

4.3.4. Varying cell location interpretation

Independently from the coordinates and their arrangement through CRSs, there is often an interpretation of a value as sitting “next” to the coordinate point, in our terminology: direct position. This seems to result from a visual misunderstanding of a grid – it is commonly accepted that the cell values in a Cartesian grid are associated with the

Fig. 11. Sample hexagonal grid described by sheared axes (Baumann and Merticariu, 2018).

exact coordinate whereas in Earth sciences cell contents often is associated with a position between neighbouring direct positions.

In our approach, and commonly in mathematics, values are associated with the exact coordinates of their direct position; in remote sensing this is referred to as “pixel in corner”, also referred to as “pixel is area”. However, a common practice in GIS is to consider a “pixel in center” position, also referred to as “pixel is point”, typically meaning: the geometric center of the grid cuboid (in 2-D: square) in a regular grid. Fig. 12 visualizes both interpretations.

Technically, this is typically described by metadata, such as tags in a TIFF file indicating an interpretation of “pixel in center” versus “pixel in corner”. Implementations such as libtiff (n.n., 2021-) use code lists which guide implementation of the processing tool. Indeed, this split interpretation is mainly driven by the GeoTIFF format, which has picked these two special cases while ignoring all others. A more general,

systematic overview on a number of such value shift cases has been established by Arakawa (Arakawa and Lamb, 1977), but it can be generalized even more to give the value a center of gravity in any direction and distance of its position as indicated by its coordinate. In the most general case the grid value is determined by a sensor-specific intensity distribution integral associated with the value’s coordinate position – a typical case is the instantaneous field of view of a sensor collecting radiosity on some area on ground.

Based on this view we prefer an explicit modelling, which does not hide the actual algorithmic treatment of data. One way of doing so is to describe a “pixel in center” situation by a coordinate shift of half a pixel size (remember this discussion only applies to regular grids), which in turn can be modelled as a concatenation of the given CRS with an engineering CRS having a correspondingly shifted origin by half the pixel size; such a CRS concatenation is explicitly foreseen in ISO 19111 (ISO, 2019a). An additional characterization would be to capture the intensity distribution, something which currently is not considered in the Earth Sciences except in very special situations of sensor calibration and validation.

In some situations this point versus area distinction can become particularly cumbersome. For example, in atmospheric research different physical parameters may be subject to different regimes with respect to position assignment relative to the coordinates. Concretely, mass of a cell may be associated with the center between neighbouring coordinates (“pixel in center”) whereas wind speed may be associated with corners, potentially even split into different corners for the u and v horizontal components.

Generally, this idea begs several questions:

- The concept is discussed on regular grids only. What would it mean in case of irregular grids?
- Discussion seems to focus on Lat/Long. What about pixel-in-X for time etc.?
- Why is it assumed that pixels have clearly delineated polygons and do not overlap? From sensor physics it rather seems that generally a pixel is obtained through a weighted integral, conceptually going from the CCD element’s center to infinity, but at least involving some neighbourhood possibly larger than the distance to the next element.
- Why is it assumed that the value of a pixel is spatially extended and constant over some neighbourhood? Interpolation will yield different values even close to a pixel. The pixel areas discussed seem to apply only to nearest-neighbour interpolation, where “nearest” already is hard to define (consider irregular grids, Kriging, etc.).
- Pixel-in-corner refers to what corner in general? 2-D has 4 corners, 3-D has 8 corners, etc. – not to mention triangular and hexagonal grids as discussed above. Further: why does the principle have to be

Fig. 12. “Pixel in center” (center; also called “pixel is point”) vs. “pixel in corner” (right; also called “pixel is area”) interpretation; geographic map display often uses a downward-pointing y axis (right).

confined to a corner vs. the center in the first place, and not at 75%? Supporting just corners seems random.

See (OGC, 2021-01b) for a recent, documented version of this recurring discussion. Altogether, we consider such variations of the grid theme to be implementation details and do not address them on this contribution's level of abstraction.

4.4. Multi-curve coverages

After addressing 0-dimensional multi-point coverages with their special case grid coverage, we move on to coverages whose delineating shapes have a non-zero topological dimension. Such coverages essentially align with geometric structures, as they appear, for example, in 3D city modelling and Computer-Aided Design (CAD).

A multi-curve coverage is a coverage consisting of a collection of curves, that is: the behaviour of the field described by the coverage is modelled through curves. A curve is given by an ordered list of two or more points, in which case it resembles a single or poly-line with straight connections, or a point list with additional curve information, such as splines (Ferguson, 1964).

By way of example, a multi-curve coverage might describe routes that have numbers and names, a pavement width and a pavement material type assigned to each segment of some road network.

Formally, the coverage evaluation function is given, for some coverage c and position p , as follows:

$$\text{evaluate}_c(p) = \{ v \mid \exists \text{ curve } x \in \text{domain}(C): x.\text{contains}(p) \}$$

The containment predicate on which this definition relies, $\text{contains}()$, refers to the corresponding probing predicate on the geometric elements contained in the coverage, such as the ones defined in ISO 19107 (ISO, 2019b). Obviously it is heavily dependent on the way the direct positions are described – through direct enumeration of the direct positions (example: point clouds), containment descriptions (example: curves, areas, and volumes), or some algorithmically involved algorithm (example: Ground Control Points in sensor models). While we allow any method on principle to specify the direct positions, we focus on the most common methods used in practice (see Section 4).

From a multi-curve coverage, a corresponding multi-point coverage can be constructed from the bounding points of the curves; often the result is unambiguously defined, but in general it depends on the representation mechanism of the curve (see next). Conversely, a multi-curve coverage can be derived from a multi-point coverage, but in the general case will not be unique.

Depending on the application, the evaluation function may return at most one element (no crossing routes, in our example), or may return several values (in case of crossings and bridges).

As the geometric description of curves is dependent on their endpoints (although maybe not completely, such as in non-straight cases) the coverage modelling becomes a 2-level hierarchy, where 1-D curves rely on 0-D points. Mappings from multi-curve to multi-point coverages are conceivable. A trivial mapping is by down-propagating all coverage values from the curves to the points and dropping the curve information. This is of less practical use than other mappings where the curves get “rendered” into series of points at some given distance (i.e., resolution). As LIDAR returns such point clouds of objects, it is of interest to study multi-curve and multi-point coverages in combination for applications such as object reconstruction; this will be of even more importance with the multi-surface and multi-solid coverages.

Direct positions on such a curve take on the value associated with the curve object; other direct positions of the coverage are undefined.

4.5. Multi-surface coverages

Continuing up the hierarchy of topological dimensions, we next

address surfaces, where 2-D elements determine the coverage domain set. A multi-surface coverage is a coverage where the direct positions are described through surfaces. The formal definition is structurally identical to the previous one, just with curves replaced by surfaces:

$$\text{evaluate}_c(p) = \{ v \mid \exists \text{ surface } x \in \text{domain}(C): x.\text{contains}(p) \}$$

From a multi-surface coverage, a corresponding multi-curve coverage can be constructed from the bounding curves of the surfaces; often the result is unambiguously defined, but in general it depends on the representation mechanism of the surface (see below). Conversely, a multi-surface coverage can be derived from a multi-curve coverage, but in the general case it will not be unique.

The description of a surface relies on a bounding curve ring (with or without holes), which in turn relies on points at both ends of each line segment; to remain unique, the bounding polygons should be planar, thereby defining a surface plane. The de-facto standard for describing curved surfaces is NURBS (Rogers, 2000), based on control points and polygons.

Direct positions on such a surface take on the value associated with the surface; other direct positions of the coverage are undefined. Various practically relevant subtypes of multi-surface coverages exist, including polyhedral surfaces and their special case of Triangulated Irregular Networks (TINs) which often are used for Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) (Kumler, 1994); ISO 19107 offers a data type TriangulatedSurfaceData (ISO, 2019b).

As an example, land use can be represented by a multi-surface coverage where the spatial domain is composed of one surface per cadastral parcel; the coverage values associated with such parcels then may constitute soil types, ownership, etc. A 3-D example is given by isosurfaces of atmospheric data such as temperature, wind speed, etc. (Fig. 13).

Multiple values again may be forbidden by design, such as isosurfaces which by definition do not cross, touch, or overlap.

In practice, multi-surface coverages can be used to model bundles of equi-potential surfaces such as air pressure in atmospheric data.

4.6. Multi-solid coverages

With coverages representing spatial bodies we reach the final hierarchy level, 3-D solids. A multi-solid coverage is a coverage where the direct positions are described through solids. The formal definition again is structurally identical to the previous ones, albeit based on solids:

$$\text{evaluate}_c(p) = \{ v \mid \exists \text{ solid } x \in \text{domain}(C): x.\text{contains}(p) \}$$

From a multi-solid coverage a corresponding multi-surface coverage

Fig. 13. Sample atmospheric simulation isolines and isosurfaces (n.n.a).

Fig. 14. Tetrahedron 3-D solid (left) and vertex/edge/surface/solid incidence graph (right) (Mahdiraji, 2015).

can be constructed from the bounding surfaces of the solids; often the result is unambiguously defined, but in general it depends on the representation mechanism of the solid (see next). Conversely, a multi-solid coverage can be derived from a multi-surface coverage, but in the general case it will not be unique.

Solids can be described in various ways, such as Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) and Boundary Representation (B-Rep). CSG (Requicha and Voelcker, 1977) relies on a small set of analytically described standard volumes, such as sphere, cylinder, cone, and torus. A concrete object consists of instantiations of these, positioned and scaled as required. By combining solids through regularized set operations, arbitrarily complex objects can be built recursively. Constructive Hyper-volume Modelling is an extension to this (Pasko et al., 2001)

Conversely, B-Rep (Braid et al., 1980) models solids through their boundary surfaces, edges, and vertices. Such graphs need to adhere to several nontrivial geometric and topological integrity constraints, including non-self intersection, singularity avoidance, planarity of the surface graph, etc.; B-Rep solids can be constructed piecewise through so-called Euler operations, which maintain all these constraints (Mäntylä) (Baumgart, 1972). An example is shown in Fig. 14.

From a coverage perspective, B-Rep is a natural way of describing solids; CSG modelling, parametric representations, etc. comprise alternatives which easily might be added.

4.7. Mixed coverages

So far we have established coverages of different types, sorted along the topological dimension of the spatio-temporal objects describing the mapping to values, plus specific extra constraints that allow modelling grids as special cases of point clouds. It is a natural next step to allow coverages with a mixed description. This bears significant practical relevance. For example, data formats like GMLJP2 (Colaiacomo et al., 2018), GDB (ESRI, 2021-), GeoPackage (OGC, 2021), and SAFE (ESA, 2021-01) all allow incorporating different data structures within the same package, not to speak about common container formats like zip and tar which are allowed by OGC CIS 1.1 as well.

Formally, let $c_i: D \rightarrow V$ for $1 = i \leq n$, $n > 0$ be coverages of any of the types introduced above, all sharing the same domain and range. Then, a mixed coverage c can be defined in a straightforward manner as

$$c: D \rightarrow V, c(p) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n c_i(p) \text{ for } p \in D$$

Mixed coverages are not currently addressed by standardization in a formal manner, which may have to do with the intrinsic complexity of the corresponding services; however, pragmatically several data formats exist (such as GMLJP2 (Colaiacomo et al., 2000)) which support such mixed data without any particular conceptual underpinning.

5. Coverage services

Although the service model is not at the heart of this contribution, we exemplarily discuss how the coverage data model can benefit encoding, provision, access, and analytics of coverages. This also gives some impression about the practical relevance and impact of the overall coverage work, of which we only report a specific part here.

Following the thrust of this paper, we prioritize standardized approaches. Further, as grid coverages form the by far most relevant category these days, we focus on those.

5.1. Coverage representation and encoding

The abstract concepts presented in this contribution define a foundation for coverage structures, but not to the level of concrete interoperability – this is achieved via a concrete implementation schema, for example the OGC/ISO Coverage Implementation Schema (CIS), derived from the 19123-1 model. Among others, CIS is concrete enough to define an extensible ecosystem of encodings allowing to express coverages in common formats like GeoTIFF, NetCDF, and many more.

A recurring problem with the plethora of data formats is their varying capability of representing metadata – even the purely technical metadata like domain CRS and range type often cannot be encoded; still, such formats are practically important as they often offer efficient binary representations, compression, etc. Conversely, informationally complete encodings where all coverage information can be carried along – such as CIS XML, JSON, and RDF – tend to be inefficient in storage footprint and access. To combine the best of these extremes, CIS has introduced a mixed representation where a container format is used for gathering a canonical header in an informationally complete format (such as XML, JSON or RDF) paired with one or more files containing range values in any suitable format. By factoring out high-volume parts such as the range sets from the header, it is possible to store them efficiently in some binary format, while retaining the complete coverage contents.

In CIS, encodings for XML, JSON, and RDF are already included as optional packages. Further formats are defined separately for GeoTIFF, NetCDF, JPEG 2000, GRIB2, etc. (OGC, 2021).

5.2. Coverage access

The purposeful step of WCS 2.0 to separate the data from service model has substantially broadened the opportunities for accessing coverages, making it possible to utilize WCS, WFS (Vretanos, 2014), WMS (de la Beaujardiere, 2006), WPS (Mueller, Pross), SOS (Bröring et al., 2012), and further service Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). However, the most comprehensive and streamlined functionality is available with the WCS suite of standards; see (Baumann, 2021-01b) for the authoritative specifications (Baumann, 2021-01b) and (Baumann

et al., 2018) for an overview. In contrast, WFS only allows retrieving a complete coverage, as it does not support multi-dimensional subsetting capabilities. WCS centers around a mandatory core which allows download of a coverage, bounding box extraction, and format encoding. Further bespoke functionality is specified in optional extensions, including range (“band”) subsetting, reprojection, data upload to the server, and datacube analytics (see next section).

Request encoding – in WCS speak: protocol binding – is uniformly through the http Web protocol, but can follow different flavours: GET/KVP, XML/POST, SOAP, and, more recently and still heavily under development, OAPI. We present GET and OAPI for comparison, both with a request on a 3-D x/y/t image timeseries, from which subsetting extracts a reduced footprint (“trim”) in Lat and Long at a particular position in time (“slice”). The GET request signals that it is a GetCoverage belonging to the WCS family, followed by the identifier of the coverage addressed and the subsetting coordinates, one per axis, and is finalized by specification of the return format:

```
http://www.acme.com/wcs?
  SERVICE=WCS & VERSION=2.0
  & REQUEST=GetCoverage & COVERAGEID=Sentinel-2
  & SUBSET=Long(100,120)
  & SUBSET=Lat(50,60)
  & SUBSET=time("2018-11-06T23:20:52")
  & FORMAT=image/png
```

Conversely, the following request does a slicing only in space, thereby focusing on a specific point on Earth, while not mentioning time at all, thereby extracting everything available along time – in case of a 2D Lat/Long coverage the result would be a single point, in case of a 3D Lat/long/time datacube, as is the case here, the result is the history of that point, conveniently expressed as comma-separated values:

```
http://www.acme.com/wcs?
  SERVICE=WCS & VERSION=2.0
  & REQUEST=GetCoverage & COVERAGEID=Sentinel-2
  & SUBSET=Long(100)
  & SUBSET=Lat(50)
  & FORMAT=text/csv
```

OAPI tries to partially avoid query parameters, preferring a pseudo-RESTful syntax to accomplish the same; here a rephrasing of the first WCS example above:

```
https://acme.com/oapi/collections/Sentinel-2/coverage?
  SUBSETS=Lat(51.9:52.1),
  Long(-4.1:-3.9),
  time("2018-11-14")
  & F=image/png
```

With the rasdaman Array DBMS the concept of Internet-accessible datacubes, amenable to individual queries and not requiring deep technical skills, was pioneered. Some of the epigons provide some sort of query language with (n.n.c) or without spatio-temporal coordinate support (paradigm4), others just a direct programming interface –

nowadays typically in python – which represents a serious security issue: any code can be submitted to the server, from anywhere, and gets executed in an unsupervised manner. Coverage-based APIs, on the contrary, offer high-level access and processing with streamlined functionality, hence easier and safer to use. An overview of 19 different datacube technologies is presented in the Research Data Alliance report (RDA, 2018).

The aforementioned rasdaman engine, which is the OGC coverage reference implementation, gives access to multi-dimensional coverages via WMS for visualization, WCS for data extraction, reformatting, and download, and WCPS for safe server-side analytics. Internally, all these operations are translated into queries of rasdaman’s array language, rasql, which has been the blueprint for the array extension to the ISO SQL query language, SQL/MDA (Multi-Dimensional Arrays) (ISO, 2019d), see (Misev and Baumann, 2015) for an overview.

5.3. Coverage analytics

OGC Web Coverage Processing Service (WCPS) is a high-level datacube analytics language with built-in spatio-temporal semantics, crafted tightly around the OGC/ISO coverage model. Through the WCS Processing extension, WCPS is tied into the overall WPS ecosystem. A WCPS request sends a query string, usually with the identifiers of one or more available coverages as input parameters, and returns a set of result scalars (in case of aggregation) or coverages. The idea is to allow “any query, any time, on any size” rather than having just a predefined set of functions, which is either too limiting or too hard to oversee. Such WCPS

expressions can range from simple extraction to any complexity and length.

Processing in the server includes data fusion with any number of coverages, filtering of coverages based on their data properties, multi-coverage analytics, and encoding results for shipping them back to the

client.

A simple example would deliver the average temperature from an ERA5 climate model at a particular geo position, across all times and all heights:

```

for $c in (ERA5)
return avg( $c[ E(494500), N(4655000) ] )

```

In the WCS suite the protocol for sending requests and receiving result sets is given by the *ProcessCoverages* request; in GET/KVP encoding the above query can be submitted through the following URL:

```

http://www.acme.com/wcs?
  SERVICE=WCS & VERSION=2.0
  & REQUEST=ProcessCoverages
  & QUERY=for $c in (ERA5) return avg($c[E(4945),N(4655)])

```

A histogram could be expressed in WCPS as

```

for $c in (ERA5)
return
  encode(
    coverage GeneralGridCoverage histogram
    domain set bucket index (0:255)
    range set count( $C.blue = bucket ),
    "text/csv"
  )

```

Due to the high-level nature of the language, complex analytics can be tasked without any programming. Further, the language is amenable to heavy optimization, parallelization, distributed processing, etc. in a fully transparent manner, without user or administrator intervention. This has been demonstrated on dozens of Petabytes with the rasdaman engine (n.n.b) (Baumann et al., 2017) which also boosts the EarthServer datacube federation (n.n., 2021-0b), the largest of its kind worldwide.

The same underlying formal framework is standardized as the SQL datacube extension, MDA (Multi-Dimensional Arrays) (ISO, 2019d), which resembles the rasdaman array query language. The underlying algebraic foundation (Baumann, 1999) and operational capability is the same as with WCPS (modulo the space/time semantics built into WCPS); in fact, rasdaman internally translates WCPS requests to MD queries for processing.

An integrated analytics language supporting all coverage types, in the spirit of database languages like, e.g., SECONDO (Güting et al., 1999) (Nidzwetzki and Güting, 2017), MQL (Mahdiraji, 2015), SQL/MDA (ISO, 2019d) and OGC WCPS (Baumann, 2010) (Baumann, 2021-01c) is a topic of further research and a forthcoming paper.

6. Conclusion

We have presented a unifying abstract model for coverages, which is in advanced status of adoption, becoming ISO 19123-1 (and updated Abstract Topic 6 in OGC) and compatible with the existing implementation standard 19123-2. While a standard has to respect diverse constraints such as requiring little domain knowledge and backwards compatibility across multiple specifications, an article like this has the scientific freedom to adopt an abstract, independent position, hence a fresh view. We hope that it fosters discussion of the forthcoming 19123-1 standard and can act as meaningful input, stimulating future evolution of coverage concepts and technology.

Our key contributions are as follows:

- We have developed a coherent framework for the representation of spatio-temporally extended phenomena, regardless of their dimension but particularly suitable for spatio-temporal data.
- The conceptualization established, to the best of our knowledge, has not been done before in a way that is equally comprehensive and suitable for deriving implementation standards for scalable, interoperable services.
- This framework is modernizing, clarifying, and enhancing the existing standards' coverage data model while remaining essentially compatible. Moreover, concepts are simple and can also be easily communicated to non-geo experts.

- A comprehensive treatment of all possible grid types is proposed, including mixed-type grids where different axes follow different patterns (such as Cartesian versus regular versus irregular).

We hope that this paper can act as a companion document to the standard, giving background on design decisions and explaining concepts, something which is not appropriate in a standard itself. The unified concepts can contribute to closing gaps in coverage modelling, and in particular for devising flexible, easy-to-use, but comprehensive and powerful Earth Data services for increasing insight on the Big Earth Data being continuously collected.

The coverage concept is at the heart of Big Earth Data Analytics: it unifies handling across all spatio-temporal dimensions; it integrates a number of essential data structures, namely regular and irregular grids, point clouds, and general meshes; it is matured through extensive discussion among a large number of data generating and consuming communities, from upstream satellite operators to downstream precision farming to name but two; and there is not only a concise, yet flexible data model, but also a versatile, powerful service model ranging from simple extraction to high-end analytics and fusion, both of which are streamlined and establish interoperability across all coverage types and formats. As more and more services emerge and data volumes grow by multi-Terabytes per day, the issues of interoperability and easy-to-use, yet powerful access and processing becomes more and more urgent. The recent quest for "analysis-ready data" underlines this. A common, well-founded coverage model, therefore, is a key pillar for powerful, user-friendly services.

Practical impact of 19123-1, which this paper anticipates, is substantial, establishing the foundations of a whole ecosystem of further standards. Within ISO we first find 19123-2, the Coverage Implementation Schema, which is a concretization of the 19123-1 concepts ready for implementation and conformance testing. Further, there is a series of additional standards using coverages: ISO 19111 geographic referencing normatively references coverages (ISO, 2019e); ISO 19115 metadata (ISO, 2014); ISO 19129 Imagery, gridded and coverage data framework (ISO, 2009a); ISO 19130 Imagery sensor models for geopositioning (ISO, 2018a); ISO 19131 Data product specifications (ISO, 2007). ISO 19136 Geographic Markup Language (GML), including coverage encoding (ISO, 2020d); ISO 19144 Classification systems (ISO, 2009b); ISO 19157 Data quality utilizing coverages for representing quality information (ISO, 2018b); ISO 19156 Observations and Measurements (O&M) (ISO, 1915); ISO 19163-2 Metadata and encoding rules for imagery and gridded data (ISO, 2020b). Most of these have their parallel in OGC. The INSPIRE legal framework for a common European Spatial Data Infrastructure relies on ISO/OGC coverages as the

basis for the conceptual models defined for various INSPIRE Themes, as well as the INSPIRE WCS specification (INSPIRE, 2021-0). Not surprisingly, a large number of open-source and proprietary tools implement coverages, their interoperability relies on a concise, adequate conceptualization.

Our own work focuses on flexible, scalable services on massive, heterogeneous, and distributed multi-dimensional datacubes, manifest in the rasdaman Array Database System. As editors of the OGC and ISO coverage standards we continuously use rasdaman as our platform for evaluating implementability, and so rasdaman naturally has become reference implementation. Various services have been deployed on basis of rasdaman, strictly based on the OGC coverage standards. WCPS-style processing at large has been demonstrated on Earth data assets exceeding 50 PB, single queries have been parallelized across more than 1000 Amazon cloud nodes, and data fusion on coverages is routine in the EarthServer federation. Hence, it is safe to say that the OGC coverage data and service models are practice-proven and allow for fast, scalable, and flexible implementations.

A long avenue of further research remains to be done, with the abstract coverage model presented here hopefully acting as a stable basis for further innovation. Most importantly, this work establishes only the data model, leaving processing and service models for future research. We list some of the challenges remaining.

Current WCS Core defines subsetting only on 0-D coverages, that is: grids and point clouds – tentatively this core has been kept as simple as possible to have a low entry barrier for implementers; more complex functionality can always be put into optional extensions. Such an extension could consider higher-dimensional subsetting (commonly also called clipping there). When considering higher-dimensional coverages there are two possible avenues. First, subsetting could be defined on multi-curve/surface/solid coverages in addition. Implementation-wise this is substantially more complex as it involves polygon clipping, and objects intersected will need to be substantially reshaped as opposed to the simple 0-D case where a point (grid or not) is either inside or outside the subsetting area.

Along the same line, the current restriction to bounding box subsetting could be lifted to allow general polygons. First steps have been undertaken by the OGC WCS MetOcean Application Schema (Trevelyan, 2021) which allows, among others, polygon “corridors” for subsetting. This is driven by an aviation use case where atmospheric conditions during a flight need to be retrieved from an x/y/z/t weather datacube to obtain the weather along the airplane’s trajectory and exactly at the time the plane passes a point, with some margin along all dimensions.

This can be generalized further to intersection between arbitrary objects where the subsetting description can be of any shape and the subsetting object can be any type of coverage. From this it is only a small step to allow general “coverage joins”, where multiple coverages sitting on a server get combined through set operations like in CAD.

Another open field of research is coverage-to-coverage transformation. Simple cases like scaling a grid coverage are well understood. However, transformations between different coverage types are also common and important, specifically between grid coverages and multi-surface coverages. Object reconstruction transforms from sampled grids to vectorial representations. Rendering conversely produces gridded representations from vectors. The famous Marching Cube algorithm (Lorensen and Cline, 1987), with its many improvements over time, is one way of obtaining a surface model from gridded data. However, although vector/raster integration is common in GISs (Piwowar, 1990) such conversion at the same time is frowned upon by some researchers, such as van der Knaap (van der Knaap, 1992): while by nature inexact in the general case, such conversions are implemented in an ad-hoc manner not based on a common agreed mathematical framework, thereby sometimes leading to unexpected results (Carver, 1994) and often not guaranteeing the same result across different tools.

Altogether, there is a huge body of research and implementation which might be consolidated into a unified coverage transformation

theory and, possibly, standard. We believe that coverages contribute essentially to better leveraging the potential of Big Earth Data, and are instrumental for understanding our planet and acting adequately across all fields, from academia to industry, from governments to citizens – we hope that the coverage fundamentals presented in this work and under standardization by ISO (and subsequently OGC) will help better our understanding of our environment.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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